

**Anonymous Survey of Student
Participation in a COVID-19 Testing Programme (saliva testing programme)**

Authors

Dr Brian Pickering¹
Professor Silke Roth
Dr Roger Tyers
Professor Jane Falkingham

License

Creative Commons Attribution License ([CC-BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/))

The following survey was implemented on *Qualtrics*.
In Section 1 (requesting engagement with the testing programme, most responses were on a 5-point Likert Scale (plus a *Not Applicable (NA)* option). *Open Field* refers to freeform comment boxes
Note that respondent selections led to branching as shown

Welcome Page

The following text was the Participant Information Sheet for the study. To proceed to the survey, potential respondents had to signal they agreed to take part and were 18 years or older at the bottom of this text.

What is the research about?

My name is Professor Jane Falkingham, Dean of the Faculty of Social Sciences at the University. I am inviting you to participate in a survey about the recent University COVID-19 Saliva Pilot Project, and participants' experience and opinions about it. The first pilot phase of this project was in June/July 2020, the second took place in September/October 2020. This anonymous survey is concerned only with the September/October pilot. It seeks to assess the experiences of those who participated, and also of those who were eligible and invited to participate, but did not.

This study was approved by the Faculty Research Ethics Committee (FREC) at the University (Ethics/ERGO/FSS Number: 61445)

What will happen to me if I take part?

This study involves completing an anonymous questionnaire which should take approximately five to ten minutes of your time. If you are happy to complete this survey, you will need to tick (check) the box

¹ Corresponding author j.b.pickering@soton.ac.uk

below to show your consent to participate. As this survey is anonymous, the research team will not know whether you have participated, or what answers you provided.

Why have I been asked to participate?

You have been asked to take part because you are a student at the University, and you were invited to take part in the September/October 2020 COVID-19 Saliva Pilot Project.

What information will be collected?

In section 1, we ask about your participation in the September/October 2020 pilot. In the section 2, we have some demographic questions. These will help us analyse whether differences in participation rates are associated with certain characteristics.

The survey is designed to be anonymous. The demographic data will not be used to attempt re-identification of participants. Consequently, your survey data cannot be linked to any other data about you (e.g. your test results from the pilot or any medical data held by the NHS, or by the University) or anywhere else. If you choose to fill out the free-text boxes, please ensure that you do not include anything that would make it possible to identify you or any other person.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

If you decide to take part in this survey, you will not receive any direct benefits; however, your participation will contribute to our understanding of how Saliva testing is carried out, and how to improve such tests in future. The ultimate goal is to improve how we test for COVID-19, in order to save lives, protect public health and enable a return to 'normal' patterns of work and education as soon as possible.

Are there any risks involved?

It is expected that taking part in this survey will not cause you any psychological discomfort and/or distress. However, should you feel uncomfortable you can leave the survey at any time.

If you require further information or advice on COVID-19 you can consult the dedicated NHS website.

If you are suffering from anxiety or mental health issues as a result of the COVID-19 pandemic and its consequences (or for any other reason) you can consult the NHS Mental Health resources or the University's Student Services.

What will happen to the information collected?

All information collected for this study will be stored securely on password protected computers and backed up on a secure server held by the University. Any free text responses you give may be quoted in publications which come from this research, but no information will be published that can identify any individual. Only the research team in the University will have access to this 'raw' information.

The information collected will be analysed and used by the University. Reports coming from the survey, fully aggregated and anonymised (e.g. removing any information provided in the free-text boxes which could potentially identify individuals), may be shared with partners in City, the NHS and Department for Health and Social Care to inform future work on COVID-19 testing. It may also be published in the form of public reports or journal articles.

The University conducts research to the highest standards of ethics and research integrity. In accordance with our Research Data Management Policy, data will be held for 10 years after this survey study has finished when it will be securely destroyed.

What happens if there is a problem?

If you have a query about this survey you can email <email address>. If you are unhappy about any aspect of this study and would like to make a formal complaint, you can contact the Head of Research

Integrity and Governance, University, on the following contact details: Email: <email address>, phone: <phone number>. Please quote the Ethics/ERGO number above. Please note that by making either a query or a complaint you will not be anonymous as you will be identifiable from your e-mail address. This cannot, of course, be linked to any responses you may have provided to the survey itself.

More information on your rights as a study participant is available via this link: <http://srv00853.soton.ac.uk:1776/content-design/participant-information.page>

Thank you for reading this information sheet and considering taking part in this research.

Please tick (check) this box to indicate that you have read and understood information on this form, are aged 18 or over and agree to take part in this survey.

The Survey

Section 1

This first section concerns your experience of the COVID-19 Testing Programme this autumn and winter (we are not asking about participation in any previous pilot programme).

1. Have you received an invitation to participate in the [CITY] COVID-19 Testing Programme run by the [UNIVERSITY] this autumn and winter?

-

-Yes, I have received an Email invitation (*go to question 2*)

-No, I heard about the programme elsewhere and found the website to register (please specify how you heard about it _____) (*go to question 2*)

-I have not been invited to take part (*go to question 9*)

2. Have you registered to take part in the programme?

-Yes (*go to question 3*),

- No (*go to question 8*)

3. Have you provided a saliva sample?

-Yes, once (*go to question 4*)

-Yes, twice (*go to question 4*)

-Yes, more than two times (*go to question 4*)

-No (*go to question 7*)

4. Please rate the following aspects of the programme. 1 = completely agree – 5 = completely disagree

- I am satisfied with my experience of the programme. 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- The instructions are easy to understand. 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- It is easy to drop off my samples. 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- I have full confidence in the programme. 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- All my household members are participating in the programme. 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- Taking part in the pilot programme and getting tested is reassuring. 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- (*Go to Question 5*)

5. What do you feel is good about the process?

- (Open field)
- (Go to Question 6)

6. What do you dislike about the process?

(Open field)
(Go to Question 12)

7. We would like to understand why you registered but have not supplied saliva samples. Please rate the following aspects of the programme. 1 = completely agree – 5 = completely disagree

- The instructions are unclear. 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- There is no nearby drop-off point for my samples. 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- I do not have confidence in how my data will be used. 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- I am concerned about receiving a positive test result 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- I am concerned that a positive test result may disrupt my own life or that of my parents/children/household members 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- I am concerned that a positive result may have financial consequences (job/mortgage etc) for me or my household members 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- I am concerned that a positive test might mean I am unable to go home at Christmas/weekends 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- I am afraid that I could get infected at the drop-off point. 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- One or more of my household members does not want me to participate in the programme. 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- Please add any further comments about why you haven't provided samples [open field]
- (Go to Question 11)

8. We would like to understand why you have not registered. Please rate the following aspects of the programme. 1 = completely agree – 5 = completely disagree

- I am not in Southampton. 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- I do not have time to participate in the programme. 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- The instructions are unclear. 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- There is no nearby drop-off point for my samples. 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- I do not have confidence in how my data will be used. 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- I am concerned about receiving a positive test result 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- I am concerned that a positive test result may disrupt my own life or that of my children/household members 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- I am concerned that a positive result may have financial consequences (job/mortgage etc) for me or my household members 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- I am concerned that a positive test might mean I am unable to go home at Christmas/weekends 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A
- I am afraid that I could get infected at the drop-off point. 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A

One or more of my household members does not want me to participate in the programme. 1 – 2 – 3 – 4 – 5 – N/A

- Please add any further comments about why you haven't registered [open field]
- (*Go to Question 11*)

9. Would you have liked to have taken part, if possible?

- Yes (*go to Question 10*)
- No (*go to Question 11*)

10. Why?

- (Open field)

You can still register to take part in the COVID-19 Testing Programme, by following the link below, which will open in a new window. But please do not forget to complete this survey.

Link: URL

- (*Go to Question 12*)

11. What could have encouraged you to take part?

- (Open field)
- (*Go to Question 12*)

12. What do you think could be improved in future programmes of this kind?

- (Open Field)
- (*Go to Question 13*)

13. Please use this box if you have any further comments.

Please keep in mind that you should not reveal your identity or the identity of others when you provide additional comments.

- (Open Field)
- (*Go to Section 2*)

Section 2.

In this last section, we have a few demographic questions. This allows us to better understand which groups have participated (or plan to participate) in the programme and which groups don't. As noted above, the survey is anonymous, but if you have any concerns please feel free to submit the survey without answering these questions.

14. Please choose the status that applies to you

- Undergraduate – UK
- Undergraduate – EU
- Undergraduate – International (non-EU)
- Postgraduate – UK
- Postgraduate – EU
- Postgraduate – International (non-EU)

(*Go to Question 15*)

*Questions 15 and 16 have been removed. **Question 15** asked for Faculty (with Institution-specific faculty names) and **Question 16** asked for Year of Study.*

17. What best describes your household?

- a. Live with other family members or partner
- b. Live with house mates in private housing.
- c. Live in student halls of residence.
- d. Live on my own.

(go to question 18)

18. If you live with a partner or housemate, do they have a job?

- Yes, my partner and/or at least one housemate is employed.
- Yes, my partner and/or at least one housemate is self-employed.
- No, partner/housemate is not employed.
- I do not live with a partner/housemate
- Don't know

(Go to Question 19)

**19. Do any children, parents or vulnerable groups live in the same household with you?
(check all that apply)**

- Yes, one or more children under 5.
- Yes, one or more children between 6 and 13.
- Yes, one or more children between 14 and 20.
- Yes, one or more elderly people (over 70)
- Yes, one or more vulnerable people (with underlying health issues)
- No

(Go To Question 20)

20. What is your age?

- 18-19
- 20-24
- 25-29
- 30-39
- 40-49
- 50+
- Prefer not to say

(Go to Question 21)

21. How would you describe your gender?

- Woman

- Man
 - Other (please specify)
 - Prefer not to say
- (Go to Question 22)*

22. How would you describe your ethnicity?

- Asian
- Black/African/Caribbean
- Mixed
- White
- Other (please specify)
- Prefer not to say

Thank you for completing this survey. Remember, once you have submitted this anonymous survey, you cannot withdraw your responses from it.